

THE DARK SIDE OF VISUAL ENTERTAINMENT MEDIA: UNVEILING ITS IMPACT ON AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract

Purpose: This research explores the link between visual entertainment media and youth aggression, focusing on factors leading to aggressive behavior in young people exposed to media violence across various platforms.

Design/Methodology: We conducted in-depth qualitative interviews with respondents across different groups. Different viewpoints were offered by this segmentation. NVIVO was used to analyse the data, and social and cognitive theories were applied to comprehend aggressive behaviour patterns.

Findings: Interviews reveal that visual entertainment media can negatively impact behavior, particularly in young, impressionable individuals. Respondents emphasized the need for content restrictions or guidelines during developmental stages to mitigate these effects.

Research Implications: The study emphasizes the impact of visual entertainment media on behavior and personality, emphasizing the need for age-appropriate media consumption guidelines and awareness of media's fantasy versus reality to prevent negative developmental effects and promote responsible media consumption.

Keywords: Aggression, Visual Media, Consumer Behaviour, General Aggression Model, Desensitization

Introduction

In recent years, researchers have developed a keen interest in the relationship between visual entertainment media and the behaviour of young individuals, particularly focusing on the connection between such media and aggressive behaviour. Visual content tailored for youth comprises a diverse range, including movies, comedy shows, video games, and online gaming. It plays a significant role in shaping perceptions, influencing social behaviour, and contributing to cognitive development among the youth. The accessibility and prevalence of these media sources contribute substantially to their influential role in shaping perspectives and preferences, especially concerning aggressive tendencies in young people.

According to statistics, India has a youth population comprising 27.5% of its total population. Research indicates that youth constitute 89% of Over-the-Top (OTT) users in India [1, 2]. Furthermore, reports suggest that India's media and entertainment industry will reach \$100 billion by 2030; The film entertainment sector has experienced an 85% growth in 2022, while the online gaming industry has grown by 34% in 2022, generating revenues of \$69 billion and \$1.6 billion, respectively [3]. These statistics suggest a significant increase in the number of users engaging with visual entertainment media sources.

Research reveals that the youth dedicate approximately 96 minutes daily to OTT platforms [4]. Additionally, young individuals invest approximately 100 minutes per day in gaming activities [5]. Moreover, the youth in India allocate around 194 minutes each day on social media and video streaming services [6]. This underscores the high level of engagement of the youth in visual entertainment media, indicating a heightened susceptibility to the influences of these sources.

A genre that promotes violence or aggressive behaviour dominates the viewership of eight out of the top ten web series in India [7]. Furthermore, the action genre prevails in nine out of the ten highest-grossing movies of 2023 [8]. The most popular genres in 2023 are Action and Adventure accounting for approximately 54% of the market share. Increased demand of action and adventure genre also influences a larger audience which majorly comprises of youth, having a greater influence on their behaviour [9].

It is important to note that visual entertainment media may not be large enough to significantly change overall crime rates but has an influence on it [10]. As per recent findings, there has been a slight increase in juvenile crime rates in India, rising from 6.7% to 7.0% in the year 2022, encompassing a total of 30,555 cases. The report indicates that a significant majority, specifically 76.2%, of juvenile offenders fall within the age range of 16 to 18 years. [11].

The objective of the current study is to investigate aggressive behaviour in young people and how visual entertainment media influences them. It is important to address that the scope of prior research papers is limited by the quantitative methodology employed in those studies. Therefore, we aim to explore this topic further and gather more detailed replies by doing the research utilizing a qualitative technique. The main goal is to look into the factors that may cause aggressive behaviour in young people who have been exposed to violent media. Therefore, the key research question is: Does the portrayal of violence in visual entertainment media influence the violent behaviour of youth?

Objectives

- To gain comprehensive insights into the diverse patterns of media consumption prevalent among the youth demographic, examining the various forms of visual content such as movies, television shows, video games, and online platforms that contribute to their media engagement.
- To identify the factors that contribute to aggressive behaviour among young individuals when exposed to media violence.

Research Methodology

The present study aims to identify factors contributing to aggressive behavior among young individuals exposed to media violence. This research adopts an exploratory, qualitative approach. To achieve its objective, a diverse sample representing the characteristics of young individuals was deemed essential. The sample was divided into three categories to obtain age-related perspectives and insights on the topic. A snowball sampling technique was employed, and structured in-depth open-ended questions were posed to a sample of 25 individuals chosen based on their patterns of visual entertainment consumption to gather pertinent information. For further understanding and analysis, social cognitive theory and the general aggression model were applied. Personal interviews yielded a substantial number of qualitative responses valuable for the study's analysis. The sample size was limited to 25 to avoid saturation and repetitive responses.

Age Group ↓	Sample Size	
	Male	Female
19-22	6	4
22-30	5	5
30 and above	1	4

Table 1: Respondent Demographics

Literature Review

Exposure to violent media has been extensively studied in relation to its effects on youth. Research has shown that youth who are exposed to violent media, such as violent TV shows, movies, and video games, are more likely to exhibit aggressive behaviour both immediately after exposure and in the long term [10, 12]. The effects of violent media exposure on youth aggression have been found to be larger than the effects of other risk factors, such as low IQ or exposure to antisocial peers [13]. However, the causal role of media violence in aggression is still debated, with some studies suggesting that the effects may be small and inflated by methodological issues [14]. It is important to note that exposure to violent media is just one factor among many that can contribute to youth aggression, and other influences, such as family environment and community violence, also play a role [15].

General Aggression Model

The General Aggression Model (GAM) is a major framework used to study the relationship between violent media and aggression. It considers the role of personal and situational variables on aggressive behaviour, including internal states and appraisal processes [16, 17]. Exposure to sexualized media content, especially when combined with violence, has negative effects on women, influencing thoughts and behaviours towards them [18]. GAM has been applied to understand aggression in various contexts, including media violence effects [19]. The General Aggression Model (GAM) provides a framework for understanding the desensitization process that can occur with repeated exposure to violent media. Initial arousal responses to violent stimuli are reduced, leading to changes in an individual's internal state and subsequent decision-making processes [18]. Additionally, the influence of media violence on aggression may be moderated by factors such as a disposition for aggression due to non-empathic parental behaviour [20]. Children and adolescents who are exposed to violent media are more likely to act aggressively, and younger people frequently copy behaviors they see in the media [21]. The GAM explains that repeated exposure to violent media can desensitize individuals and alter their cognitive frameworks, leading to increased acceptance of aggression as a normative behavior [22].

Social cognitive theory

Social cognitive theory has been extensively used to understand the effects of media violence on behaviour [23, 20]. The theory emphasizes the role of cognitive processes, such as observational learning and outcome expectations, in shaping behaviour [24]. Research has shown that exposure to violent media, including television, movies, video games, and the internet, can lead to short-term and long-term harmful effects, such as increased aggression, desensitization to violence, and decreased prosocial behaviour [25]. Additionally, media violence can influence attitudes and beliefs about violence, leading to the normalization of aggressive behaviour. It suggests that individuals' media selection behaviour is influenced by their cognitive schemas, personal

capabilities, and outcome expectations [18]. Children and adolescents often imitate violent behaviors seen in media, leading to increased aggression and violent behaviour in real life. Social Cognitive Theory emphasizes the interplay between personal factors (e.g., self-efficacy) and environmental influences (e.g., media exposure), which shape aggressive behaviors. [26]

Analysis And Findings

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the content obtained from semi structured interviews. According to Guest et al., (2012), thematic analysis encompasses searching across data for identification of patterns, themes, that cut across individuals, settings or time. The first part of the interview was focused on collecting demographic information and the second half of the interview was focused on gathering the opinions of the interviewees on the various aspects of viewing violent content through various media.

The interviews were then analysed with NVIVO. Interview transcripts were carefully coded into NVIVO. The coded interviews were then used to generate a variety of outputs, such as word clouds and themes based on the responses, in order to gain detailed insights and information from the interviews.

The research study further used "Deductive Thematic analysis", this is also known as top-down or theory-driven approach. As mentioned earlier the study was based on GAM and social cognitive theory, these two theories were used as a basis to identify the patterns or behaviour.

Findings on the Diverse Patterns of Media Consumption

Based on data on consumption patterns, it can be concluded that there are distinct preferences and trends among the audience we can understand that thriller genre is more popular among youth. While, next preferable genre is romantic comedy and adventure. It can also be concluded that there are distinct preferences and trends among the audience the most preferred type of visual entertainment media are movies among all age groups, whereas games are equally popular with movies among youth.

Interview Questions

"Respondents were asked to give their opinion on behavioural changes observed in an individual who is exposed to violent media with the question "Have you observed behavioural/personality changes in any person who is extremely exposed to violent media?"

Drawing from the interview transcripts, it became evident that various respondents, including parents and college students, expressed concerns about observed personality changes in individuals. This shared concern across different audience segments suggests a need for media companies to address the issue. Notably, parents and siblings raised alarm when they observed children exhibiting temper tantrums after engaging in First Person Shooting (FPS) games. Based on information considered from interviews using NVIVO, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'impulsive,' 'games,' and 'playing' with higher frequency. This indicates that an impulsive behaviour is shown among the kids playing video games and personality development is affected

Respondents were asked their preference of media consumption alone versus with others with the question "Are there differences in your media preferences when consuming content with others versus alone?"

The majority of respondents indicated discomfort when viewing certain content in the presence of others compared to when they are alone. They expressed caution about what they watch with their parents and younger siblings. This apprehension may suggest a degree of fear and social stigma associated with consuming "A" rated content. Additionally, a few respondents highlighted the ambiguity in movie ratings, emphasizing the need for stricter classification. They suggested that movies with high levels of violence should either receive an "A" rating or a "U/A -16+" certification. Based on information considered from interviews using NVIVO, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'watching,' 'mental' and 'state' with higher frequency. This suggests that consuming similar content with others may affect their mental state.

Respondents were asked to give their opinion on perception towards cultural and societal norms with the question "Does violent media influence your perception on cultural and social norms?"

It was observed that violent media indeed influences people's perceptions of social and cultural norms. Some media portrayals suggest that actions like hurting women are acceptable because they demonstrate care in the end, back answering elders is permissible, and being aggressive in public places is normalized. Movies such as "Thappad," "Animal," and "Arjun Reddy" seem to contribute to the normalization of these behaviours, implying that they are integral aspects of social and cultural norms. Based on information considered from interviews using NVIVO, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'change', 'content', 'cultural' and

'communities' with higher frequency. This indicates that after consumption of media there is a change in perception about cultural and social norms among the youth.

Respondents were asked to give their opinion on force fitting of violence in with the question "What factors influence you to engage with violent media content?"

The factors influencing engagement with violent media, as indicated by respondents, encompass peer influence, reviews, and the allure of celebrity images. When alone, individuals are more susceptible to these influences, driving them to consume content with violent themes. The impact of peer opinions, critical reviews, and the fascination with celebrities collectively shape the decision-making process, highlighting the multifaceted nature of media consumption choices. Based on information considered from interviews using NVIVO, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'movie', 'peer' and 'celebrity' with higher frequency. This indicates that these are the factors that influence the audience to engage with violent content.

Respondents were asked to give their opinion on influence of peers on media consumption "Does your peer pressure make a difference when watching content?"

Based on the interviews it was identified that peer group had a significant influence on the choice of content. It impacted towards a very negative influence where the consumption pattern changed and the genres preferred later were aggressive and violent. Indicating that the immediate social circle affects the choice of media consumption. Based on the analysis of the word cloud, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'influence', 'watch' and 'content' with higher frequency. This indicates that it is evident peer pressure does make difference when it comes to consuming content.

Respondents were asked to give their opinion on lack of emotional response to a realistic portrayal of distressing situation in media "Does realistic portrayal of distressing situation in media affect your emotional response?"

The respondents mentioned that there were instances when they didn't really care about incidents that happened to them. They also noted that repeated exposure to similar occurrences through media had desensitized them, making these experiences not significantly impactful in real life. Based on information considered from interviews using NVIVO, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'emotional', 'crying' and 'connection' with higher frequency. This indicates that the audience mentioned about their lack feeling of connection and emotional response towards real life incidents

Respondents were asked to give their opinion on frequent exposure to violent content in childhood with the question "Do you think frequent exposure to violent content during childhood or adolescence may render the audience numb towards violence in the later stages of life?"

The participants emphasized the significant effects of exposure to violence in the media on children, considering their impressionable age. They emphasized how early exposure to violence affects a person's attitudes and responses to it. Significantly, respondents pointed out that people typically grow desensitized to violence as they get older, indicating that early exposure is important in forming people's long-term perceptions and emotional reactions to violent content. Based on information considered from interviews using NVIVO, it can be inferred that respondents have used the words 'age', 'violence', 'children' and 'mentality' with higher frequency. This suggests that consuming violent content at an impressionable age would affect their mentality

The interview transcripts were uploaded and coded in NVIVO, and the following themes were identified

Aggression

Studies have shown that exposure to violent media content can increase the likelihood of aggressive behaviour in the short term as well as over time [27].

In the current study, several interviewees have used the term "aggression" to express their concerns about the impact of watching violent media. A primary concern arises from parents who observed spikes in aggression in their children after playing video games. Even the young respondents acknowledged experiencing aggression while playing games, which has now become a part of their behaviour. The forceful incorporation of aggression in many movies and content has proven to be a major concern for many, especially during early childhood.

Desensitization

Desensitization refers to the process in which a person's emotional reactions to a stimulus diminish over time with repeated exposure [18]. In the context of media, desensitization can occur when individuals become less responsive to violence and suffering portrayed in media content [27]. Research has shown that exposure to violent media can lead to desensitization, resulting in decreased emotional distress and empathy towards others'

suffering [27, 14, 15]. This desensitization can have negative consequences, such as reduced likelihood of helping others in need and increased tolerance for violence [28].

In the current study, several interviewees have mentioned the term "desensitization" when asked about their response to stimuli. The young respondents, in particular, emphasized repeated exposure to violent media as a significant factor contributing to desensitization. They pointed out that the normalization of frequent exposure to violent media is a major cause of a diminished emotional response to various situations.

Hostile Appraisals

Hostile appraisals can be influenced by exposure to violent media. Research has shown that violent media can lead to hostile appraisals, which include perceiving ambiguous actions as aggressive, perceiving social interactions as aggressive behaviour, and expecting others to react aggressively in potential conflicts [27]. These hostile biases in appraisal and decision processes can contribute to increased likelihood of aggression [29]. Additionally, exposure to violent media can elicit negative emotional reactions, which involves a mixture of emotions like anger, disgust, and contempt [30].

In the current study, most interviewees emphasized the influence of visual entertainment media on hostile appraisals among themselves and their friends. They expressed the belief that media exposure leaves a predominantly negative impression on the viewer. Many provided examples from anime and superhero movies wherein heroes are portrayed as super powerful, hot-headed, and often angry in various scenes. The fact that superheroes and anime characters serve as idols for the current generation was mentioned as a significant influence, leading to the recreation of such scenes in real life. This recreation, in turn, is seen as contributing to the long-term influence on the viewer's hostile appraisals.

Parental Upbringing and Societal Norms

Parents play a significant role in influencing their children's exposure to media violence. Research shows that parental mediation, which involves parent-child interactions about media, can alter children's responses to televised relational aggression [31]. The impact of media exposure on aggressive behaviours can be influenced by various factors such as social norms derived from parents and peers. Research has shown that social norms, particularly those derived from peers, can reinforce or mitigate the impact of media content on aggressive behaviour, including cyber aggression [12]. Furthermore, media can influence beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours through both individual and social channels [32].

In the current study, several interviewees have mentioned parental upbringing as a key factor that influenced their media consumption habits. They noted that parental monitoring and restrictions set by elders prevented them from consuming media violence at a young age. They also emphasized the increased necessity of such guidance in today's media landscape, where visual entertainment media is more prone to presenting violent content unsuitable for a young audience.

While discussing societal norms, respondents highlighted the significant role of media in shaping their perceptions of cultural and societal norms. Many respondents provided examples of scenarios and real-life incidents where the presentation of scenes depicting unethical activities as good or protective led people to believe that such actions are acceptable in society.

Psychographic Characteristics

Personality, attitude, and behaviour can be influenced by media exposure. Research has shown that media violence can desensitize viewers, leading to more pleasant arousal and increased availability of aggressive cognitions [27]. Normative beliefs, influenced by media and parental behaviour, can mediate the effects of media violence consumption and non-empathic parental behaviour on violent behaviour [20].

In the current study, several interviewees, particularly the young population, emphasized the impact of excessive consumption of visual entertainment media on their psychographic characteristics, such as behaviour, personality, and attitudes. They noted a negative change in psychographics for themselves and their similarly exposed friends and relatives of the same age, primarily due to high exposure to violent media. Many of them mentioned becoming more short-tempered and restless after frequent consumption of violent media. They also mentioned a major change in how they approached handling ordinary life circumstances.

Impressionable Age

Impressionable age can be defined as the period when children are particularly receptive, absorbing information and forming mental impressions, whether accurate or erroneous. Hence, it becomes crucial to exercise caution

with younger individuals and monitor the content they are exposed to during this developmental stage. The study indicates a shared concern among parents and youth regarding the potential impact of content consumed during the impressionable age on the individual's later stages of life. This underscores the importance of being mindful about the media and materials that children are exposed to, recognizing their potential long-term effects on mental and emotional development.

Conclusion

The findings underscore the significant influence of visual entertainment media, often leaning towards the negative spectrum, on individuals' behaviour and personality. Participants emphasized the necessity of implementing restrictions or guidelines for media consumption, particularly for impressionable age groups. The study contributes valuable insights into the diverse patterns of media consumption prevalent among the youth, examining various forms of visual content such as movies, television shows, video games, and online platforms. Movies remain the most preferred type of visual entertainment media, and the influence of peer pressure on media consumption choices is evident.

Social cognitive theories, including the General Aggression Model, have been applied to understand and analyse the behavioural patterns and aggression observed among the respondents. The study identifies aggression, desensitization, and hostile appraisals as key themes emerging from the qualitative data.

Moreover, the research sheds light on the influence of parental upbringing and societal norms in shaping individuals' responses to media content. Parents play a pivotal role in influencing media consumption habits, and societal norms portrayed in media can impact individuals' perceptions of cultural and social norms.

The research findings have implications for addressing the potential negative impact of visual entertainment media on individuals' development and well-being. The study contributes to the existing literature by offering detailed insights through a qualitative approach, enriching the understanding of the impact of violent media consumption across different age groups.

In conclusion, the research highlights the need for proactive measures to mitigate the potential adverse effects of media violence on the youth, considering the increasing engagement with visual entertainment media in an emerging economy like India.

Policy Implications

India is facing an onslaught of OTT platforms and Indian youth; adolescents are bombarded with content of varying types. Based on the findings of the current research study there is a growing concern among the parents about the content exposure to adolescents.

The Information & Broadcasting ministry in India is currently very active and trying to regulate content which is unacceptable. Recently I&B ministry has blocked 18 OTT platforms for obscene and vulgar content. There is a constant emphasis by the I&B ministry not to propagate abuse and vulgarity (Pandey, 2024). But in the garb of contextual content, many OTT platforms have been indulging in profanity to use as a shock factor and attract audience. Even though there are laws against slander and sedition, punitive action can be taken only if evidence exists for direct correlation between violence and speech. Stricter rules do prevail under 3(1)(b) of the 2021 regulations, including content that violates India's national security, however stronger rules are required to regulate the content viewed by adolescents as they are the future of our nation.

According to [33], the average TV viewing time among adolescents ranges anywhere between 1.3 hours to 7.1 hours a day. Thanks to easy access to mobile phones, the average would be tilted towards the higher value. Based on the findings of the current study, it is recommended that a stricter media policy is churned out to block access of content which is violent in nature till the age of adolescence. It is also recommended that educational institutes sensitize the audience on the impact of viewing violent media and try to influence self-regulatory mechanism among the youth.

Managerial Implications

The current research study is one of its kind as it tries to assess the impact of viewing violent media within the context of India using qualitative research methods. Children tend to imbibe a lot of qualities through observational learning. Research studies [34] have indicated that adolescents who are exposed to violence or are victims of violence in their homes or communities are more likely to use violence themselves. Children cannot discriminate between reality and fantasy. And hence viewing violent media can be detrimental to their behaviour either in short term or long term.

The study is of immense value in an emerging economy like India where there is an increasing number of working couples, where children are either left under the supervision of their grandparents or caretakers. Strengthening the argument provided by Perry (2014), the current study also identified that violent media consumption leads to aggression. The current study is a contribution to the lack of literature in assessing the impact of violent media consumption across different age groups. One of the major concerns is that when aggression becomes a part of behaviour, it becomes difficult to get rid of the behaviour, hence we need to control it at the earliest possible stage.

Limitations

The current research study is based on a small sample size and is cross sectional. The study would have been more effective if the data was collected at multiple time durations to understand the behavioural impact better. The study was limited to audience in Bengaluru, the media consumption patterns may differ in a Tier II or Tier III cities.

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